
Cyber-Physical Systems - Investing for our Technology Sectors and Future European Markets

A companion recommendations white paper to the HiPEAC Vision 2026

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) research provides fundamental grounding across many contributing technology domains as a facilitator for their integration into sectors like transport, health, manufacturing and space. This integrative capacity will play a key role in bringing the full benefits of the Next Computing Paradigm to the dependable systems within these sectors. Meanwhile, there is a need to look at our supporting infrastructure for carrying out such research, where some changes will bring enormous impact, in particular for physical AI interactions with the real world. More generally, it is important to raise awareness that work on technology integration is an important factor for supporting technology transfer in general and building European technology markets.

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Introduction

As a research topic, cyber-physical systems (CPS) bring diverse technologies into cohesive wholes, that interact seamlessly with the physical world. These composite technologies require the blending of many stakeholder knowledge domains, which have been described in an associated white paper^[1]. Their applications are wide, including sectors like healthcare, manufacturing, transportation, and space. They increasingly function as regulated, evolving infrastructures spanning organisational and national boundaries, requiring coordinated governance, lifecycle management, and distributed assurance mechanisms. The research requires consideration of the cross-cutting challenges between the contributing knowledge domains, supporting technology integrations centred around computing for physical interactions. The next computing paradigm (NCP), proposed by HiPEAC, provides the infrastructure enabling a new frontier of computing support capacity. In relation to this, facilitating technology integration particularly for real world interactions will be an important accelerator.

The increasing interconnectivity of systems presents significant challenges, including the interaction complexity of diverse stakeholder knowledge domains (across technology specializations, end users, policy, regulation, standards, the public, etc.), orchestration, dependability and the scalability of solutions. This means CPS research, while playing an important role as a market creator, has unique challenges compared with most other research domains, because it can require taking them all into account. This calls for us to re-examine the supportive tools, frameworks, and policies for doing research - creating an evolved separate and distinct approach for handling much more advanced integrative research. As a metaphor upgrading our building technologies and approaches from those for houses to those enabling skyscrapers.

The recommendations in this paper consider the cross-cutting challenges between two or more of the contributing knowledge domains, with respect to enabling physical interactions. We make a distinction between the more familiar *Applied R&D* technologies, advancing technology inside the CPS and their integrations, and *Support R&D* technologies^[2], which refer back to our analogy and enhance the means for composite technology development. The recommendations are aimed to support policymaking for R&D as well as to directly inform research calls or project set-up, from research community and support actions to R&D advancement actions. They are presented with their rationale, as well as outcomes and scope as seen in research programmes. Before detailing each one, we list them here:

Governance Capacity

- *Create a pan-European research association to represent needed advances for complex and critical systems. (Support R&D Community and Policy)*
- *Foster collaborative R&D efforts between AI, dependable systems research, and domain application experts. Includes convergence with emerging AI regulation and certification. (Support R&D Community and Policy)*
- *Value-chain risk sharing (Applied R&D Community and Policy)*

Assured AI & Integrative Capacity

- *Launch support R&D technologies facilitating integrations between contributing CPS knowledge domains. (Support R&D Technology)*
- *Decentralised Learning and End-to-End AI Lifecycle Management for CPS Big Data (Support R&D Technology)*
- *Open-up safety-security-performance interactions for real-world resilience and technology uptake in systems as markets. (Applied R&D Technology).*
- *Advance proactive risk management and analysis solutions for enhanced dependability of systems interactions and for AI/ML. (Applied R&D Technology)*
- *Extend online feedback mechanisms for testing and validation in dependable systems. (Applied R&D Technology)*

Scalable Infrastructure Capacity

- *With higher critical system interconnectivity, new and advanced systemic technologies for performance characterisation and for isolation of hazards and threats are needed. (Applied R&D Technology)*
- *Hybrid Edge–Cloud Big Data Analytics for CPS (Applied R&D Technology)*
- *Fleet-scale Trustworthy IIoT for Safety-Critical CPS (Applied R&D Technology)*

Governance Capacity

Three recommendations are proposed to support policy and ecosystem development.

Community and Policy Recommendation A – Create a pan-European research association to represent needed advances for complex and critical systems.

Rationale: These systems are composite technologies, whose integrations for real-world applications face unique challenges different from traditional domain-specific developments. A key issue is cohesion; while industry has programs to ensure continuity and integration, similar support is needed in advanced integrative research. Another challenge is ensuring adequate representation of these advanced technologies in research programs, crucial for Europe. This is because such technologies are ultimately infrastructures representing significant markets towards which many of our technology investments are destined – domains like transport, health and space. Furthermore, a majority of our national system engineering networks are part of a US association and advise the US on research, which isn't a problem in itself except that we don't have an equivalent EU level association to advise our policy.

There is a need for an association to unify cross-domain research integrations, providing cohesion among academia, industry, and regulatory bodies. It should include focuses on knowledge management, supporting longer development cycles, and refining cross-disciplinary collaboration. Without higher-level guidance, progress in complex CPS research is limited, much like construction projects that change teams frequently. Additionally, disruptive technologies like quantum computing can shift global development directions, requiring adaptable guiding strategies for creating composite technologies.

It will enable representation at the European level, providing a missing element for supporting European market capture, supporting and retaining European technologies, and fostering longer-term value generation including points typically beyond the direct scope of industry efforts.

Expected Outcomes:

- **Centralised Collaboration Platform:** Create a platform supporting cross-domain knowledge exchange and joint initiatives among European CPS researchers and industry partners.
- **Standardisation Advocacy:** Develop guidelines and best practices to align research outputs with emerging European standards and certification needs.
- **Educational Programs:** Coordinated agreements on normalised approaches for training to equip researchers with skills in cross-disciplinary CPS methodologies.
- **Funding Access:** Both in terms of the association operation and also advising on funding for aggregative-type CPS research projects across Europe.

Scope: This work aims to establish a research association that connects European researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers that contribute to composite technologies in complex and critical systems. The association will have a unifying influence supporting collaboration and cross-cutting research between knowledge domains; public understanding of the importance of CPS; supervisory support to draw together a common body of knowledge; and developing talent in order to maintain Europe's leadership and sovereignty of diverse technology aggregations for multi-sector applications including transport, manufacturing and health.

The association should rally Europe's existing national engineering bodies calling also on support from international groups like INCOSE, the IET and HiPEAC, as well as related focus groups like Modelica and INTO-CPS in order to have a representation of CPS and system-level research interests at the Europe level.

Key areas of focus will include analyzing how CPS-specific and integrative technologies are advancing and assessing the flow of funding to the contributing communities, highlighting both benefits and risks of underfunding. Lighthouse initiatives in various programs may offer valuable insights for structuring and managing such collaborations. The association will also prioritise building a comprehensive body of knowledge and promoting engineering education for multi-group composite technologies. Additionally, it will balance local, national, and European interests, with cross-border digital innovation hubs complementing regional or national initiatives.

In terms of policy, the association will consider how EU business data protection (such as a B2B equivalent to GDPR) affects CPS advancements, ensuring that these policies support technological progress. By facilitating access to funding opportunities, the association will empower aggregative-type research, driving innovation in critical system applications throughout Europe and boosting technology market creation.

Community and Policy Recommendation B - Foster collaborative R&D efforts between AI, dependable systems research, and domain application experts. Includes convergence with emerging AI regulation and certification.

Rationale: *The integration of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) into Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) has moved from a research aspiration to an operational and regulatory imperative. The EU AI Act, now in staged implementation (high-risk systems from August 2026; AI embedded in regulated products from August 2027), creates specific obligations for AI-enabled CPS across many sectors. This demands a shift from abstract "trustworthy AI" principles towards "assured AI in context"; where assurance is system-specific, domain-specific, and integrated with existing safety certification regimes (such as ISO 26262, IEC 61508, DO-178C, IEC 62443). Coordinated efforts are essential in developing domain-specific guidelines, codes of practice, standards, and certification processes that satisfy both functional safety requirements and AI-specific compliance obligations. This collaboration is particularly crucial in high-risk domains including autonomous vehicles, smart grids, medical devices, and critical infrastructure, where AI experts must work in close conjunction with domain specialists, safety engineers, and regulatory bodies.*

Drawing parallels from the aviation industry's successful integration of fly-by-wire systems, a similar crossdisciplinary approach is imperative for AI/ML in CPS. By adopting this collaborative model, stakeholders can ensure that AI/ML-enabled CPS meet stringent dependability requirements while effectively leveraging the capabilities of AI/ML.

Expected Outcomes:

- *Establish a European network of excellence in AI/ML-enabled CPS that bridges AI research, dependable systems engineering, domain expertise, and regulatory competence.*
- *Develop domain-specific AI assurance frameworks for high-impact CPS sectors, mapping EU AI Act requirements to existing functional safety standards and certification pathways.*
- *Create harmonised guidelines and certification processes for AI/ML integration in critical systems, addressing the full AI lifecycle from development through deployment to post-market monitoring.*
- *Define stakeholder-differentiated explainability requirements: technical explanations for engineers, actionable rationale for operators, compliance evidence (model cards, datasheets, audit trails) for regulators, and calibrated trust indicators for end users.*
- *Establish reference architectures for human-AI teaming assurance, addressing joint performance validation, failure modes at handoff points, and maintenance of meaningful human oversight.*

Scope: This initiative aims to establish collaborative platforms that unite AI researchers, dependable systems experts, domain specialists, and regulatory bodies across Europe. A central activity will be developing shared understanding of how EU AI Act conformity assessment maps to domain-specific certification processes, supported by controlled lifecycle protocols for AI updates, retraining, and adaptation in deployed CPS. The work will advance test methodologies for joint human-AI performance validation and build a cross-sector repository of best practices, assurance patterns, and case studies. Interdisciplinary education efforts will equip the next generation of engineers with competencies spanning AI, safety engineering, and regulatory compliance.

The initiative will cultivate partnerships with European regulatory bodies, standardisation organisations (including CEN, CENELEC, ETSI), and notified bodies to ensure research outcomes align with regulatory expectations and support the development of harmonised standards for AI in CPS.

Community and Policy Recommendation C - Value-chain risk sharing

Rationale: As the complexity of cyber-physical systems increases rapidly, a multitude of actors become involved across the value chain in the development, manufacturing, deployment, operation, maintenance, market and operational surveillance of these systems. Interdependence of these actors, as well as of the parts of the system they are responsible for increases similarly. Consequently, liability and certification risks must be distributed across suppliers, integrators, and operators. An incipient example is provided by the AI Act in which providers and deployers are entrusted with distinct responsibilities. The approach should be applied also in general to CPS, in order to achieve a more expedient production result. In fact, the traditional model - where the "prime" contractor or final brand owner bears all legal and regulatory risk - is unsustainable for complex, multi-tiered value chains. Instead, risks must be consciously allocated, shared, and managed across different players. As a matter of fact, for suppliers, integrators and operators distributed liability risks should establish the financial and legal responsibility for specific failures, harm produced or non-performance, while certification risks, particularly in industries highly regulated should detail the responsibility for ensuring and proving that a component or system meets stringent safety and performance standards set by authorities, in both cases in a shared manner. Due to the complexity of the "System of Systems" no single entity has complete knowledge or control over every part. The integrator cannot feasibly guarantee every supplier's deep-tier sub-component. If suppliers bear no liability or certification risk, they may prioritise cost-cutting over quality and safety. Allocating risk ensures they have "skin in the game." Concentrating all risk on the integrator makes projects financially volatile and can stifle innovation. Spreading risk makes large projects more insurable and investable. The approach is necessary because certifying bodies increasingly demand transparent traceability and clear accountability throughout the supply chain. They require integrators to have robust oversight and suppliers to have mature quality management systems. However, operators also have their role in providing feedback on system features during operation.

Expected outcomes:

- **Recommendations for regulation supported policy development** to facilitate the coordination among the actors; regulation also needs to approach and help establish in a general manner liability and certification requirements for each piece of the chain
- **A policy framework** for rapid and organic feedback, based on a flexible collaboration between technology and regulatory processes on failures or gaps and their remedy in the applicable regulatory and/or standardisation system(s)
- **New approaches to defining contracts**, as the primary tool to be used, for instance:
 - Inclusion of Warranties and Indemnities: suppliers warrant their parts meet specs and indemnify the integrator against failures
 - Introduction of Limitation of Liability: caps on financial exposure for each party
 - Usage of Flow-Down Clauses: obligations (especially certification and quality requirements) are "flowed down" from integrator to Tier 1, and from Tier 1 to Tier 2 suppliers
 - Inclusion of new insurance schemes: e.g all parties carry professional liability, product liability, and errors & omissions insurance; both liability and insurance to be distributed among the actors; the structure of this insurance program to be coordinated

- *Consider introduction of co-design processes, when actors in the value chain contribute in a shared manner to the design activity of the technology/product .*
- **Certification Agreements:** *e.g. an OEM (integrator) grants a Supplier the authority to perform certification activities on its behalf, but with clear boundaries and oversight; the supplier must provide a Declaration of Design and Performance (DDP) or similar.*
- **Development of Revenue/Profit-Sharing Models:** *e.g. in some models the supplier shares in operational revenue and risk, aligning long-term incentives for reliability.*

Scope: In terms of the general policy framework the aim is to help construct the dialogue and bridge the gap between regulation, standardisation and technology in times when things are coming to market too fast and focus on accelerating feedback loops, particularly of failure cases that might be outside of the usual regulatory norms. It is of paramount importance to rethink the balance between regulation and standardisation and the role of technology developers in this. This does not necessarily need to create new and more detailed regulation/standards, rather to set the framework of requirements for the actors of the chain. Further on, existing regulation and standardisation might be updated in order to foster adaptation of liability and certification regimes to a distributed risk approach across the value chain. As such this implies a change of attitude in terms of requirements in both regulatory and standardisation bodies. This should also provide background to address management of and settle relations among the actors of the value chain. Among these are asymmetric power (when a large integrator can impose harsh terms on smaller suppliers, potentially squeezing their margins and pushing all risk downstream, which can be destabilising), opacity (as integrators may not have visibility into a supplier's sub-suppliers - Tier 2, Tier 3 -, creating "blind spots" where critical risks can hide), the Blame Game (i.e. when a failure occurs, litigation can erupt over whether it was a design flaw - integrator's responsibility -, a manufacturing defect - supplier's -, or operational misuse - operator's; clear contracts and fault-tree analysis are critical) and the issue of innovation vs. risk aversion (as heavy liability on suppliers can make them overly cautious, stifling the adoption of novel, potentially better and innovative technologies).

Assured AI & Integrative Capacity

Here we consider integrative, dependability and AI lifecycle technologies. There are five recommendations including both support and applied R&D technologies.

Technology Recommendation D – Launch support R&D technologies facilitating integrations between contributing CPS knowledge domains.

Rationale: *CPS are the assembly of technologies into higher-order technologies for real-world interactions. This means they represent EU capacity to absorb new technologies, but they also face distinct challenges from typical contributing or component technologies, as advances must satisfy many stakeholders. Research often operates in isolated silos, hindering the effective combination of advances from diverse fields like IoT, AI, and those related to dependability for CPS development. We also face increasing integration challenges for the Next Computing Paradigm, as well as sovereignty concerns requiring that CPS be ready to adopt new EU technologies.*

This calls for a new dimension of R&D with a different mindset, encompassing research, production, and policy. It will investigate technologies supporting particularly integrative R&D.

Just as we have more advanced support tools for complex construction, like JCBs, we can establish more advanced technologies supporting complex\integrative research that will greatly bring down the related effort. These will facilitate integration between contributing CPS knowledge domains, broaden access to the bigger picture for greater impact, and prepare the destination for complex new technologies. Developing these integrating solutions will provide smoother knowledge transfer and boost collaboration between researchers. They should focus on support of assets identified by projects, programmes, and industry that have been traditionally outside their scope and be refined in applied R&D projects.

This will enhance the ability to address multi-dimensional challenges, including those arising from differing values, time and space needs from stakeholder knowledge domains, for integrative work destined to sectors like transport, healthcare, and manufacturing. In parallel, applied R&D projects on complex systems would benefit by reserving effort to use and enhance these support R&D technologies. Such work transcends the traditional expectation that one person or group can advance a technology, requiring us to rethink approaches to multi-group solutions.

Expected Outcomes:

- **Integrative Support R&D:** Especially tools and approaches easing knowledge transfer between diverse expertise in CPS, but also evaluation techniques supporting new complex cross-domain work, project progress and post-project impact.
- **Cross-domain Data Sharing Platforms:** Create data-sharing platforms to improve access to the big picture across CPS contributing domains for joint analysis.
- **Implementation Readiness Research:** Understanding and preparing the complex multi-stakeholder environment of CPS-technologies, with TRL advancement and uptake.
- **Early Users:** New regular users established with projects or programmes and across the contributing CPS domains. Feedback loops should be established.

Scope: This work will focus on promoting knowledge sharing by developing integrating tools, methodologies, and platforms to enhance collaboration across domains in complex systems. These technologies should promote access to the bigger picture and be open source as a baseline. Such resources will directly support advanced research projects across CPS sectors. Preparing the environment is essential for industry and researchers to engage effectively with diverse stakeholders. Projects should focus on facilitating collaboration on multi-dimensional challenges. This includes tools for iterative improvement, such as incentives, performance measures, and mentoring schemes, ensuring continuous advancement. Managed contributions like open-source results should align with business models and sustainable maintenance strategies.

The work should also consider industrial processes adaptations to integrate new technologies, lifting constraints on the product side to maximize innovation. A complementary approach to Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), for “composite technologies,” or CTRLs, is encouraged to assess the maturity of technologies formed by the integrations of others, up to CPS, rather than individual components or interfacing. Moreover, studies should guide industry towards long-term strategies, potentially advocating regulatory changes that balance short-term competitive goals with sustained, long-term value generation. Such studies would fill a gap in

technology integration research, supporting long-term strategic adaptation to technological advancements. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Technology Recommendation E — Decentralised Learning and End-to-End AI Lifecycle Management for CPS Big Data

Rationale: Cyber-physical systems (CPS) increasingly rely on large volumes of data generated across organizational and national boundaries. This data has high economic and societal value, but it is often sensitive, safety-critical, or subject to strict legal and ethical constraints. To address this, decentralized data analysis approaches, such as federated learning, allow organizations to jointly develop AI models without transferring or centralizing raw data. This supports European priorities on data sovereignty, privacy, and cross-border collaboration, as set out in initiatives such as the European Data Strategy and sectoral data spaces. However, experience shows that decentralized learning alone is not sufficient. CPS deployments also require end-to-end management of the AI lifecycle from assessing data quality and training models, through validation and deployment, to continuous monitoring, accountability, and eventual retirement. Without such governance, risks emerge related to safety, bias, cybersecurity, and non-compliance with evolving EU regulatory frameworks, including the EU AI Act, specifically upon ownership change.

This advice therefore focuses on practical, compliance-ready approaches that help public and private actors deploy AI in CPS in a way that is trustworthy, transparent, and aligned with European risk-management standards. Internationally recognized frameworks (such as NIST and ISO guidance) are treated as operational tools that can be adapted to European legal and industrial contexts, rather than as abstract compliance obligations.

Expected Outcomes:

- **Data-sovereign decentralized AI for CPS and related technology domains (including SoS)**, enabling large-scale cross-organizational and cross-border collaboration without centralizing raw data. This includes mechanisms that respect data ownership, locality constraints, and sector-specific data-space requirements, ensuring that value creation from Big Data does not compromise control over sensitive or safety-critical information.
- **Enhanced visibility, governance, and interoperability of data elements across decentralized AI lifecycles**, through privacy-preserving and trust-enabling technologies (e.g., secure aggregation, encrypted feature exchange, shared data-provenance metadata, and cross-domain semantic models). These mechanisms support transparent data use, lawful data transfer, and verifiable data lineage across CPS and SoS deployments, strengthening auditability and public trust.
- **End-to-end lifecycle governance toolchains for distributed and federated AI**, providing modular, interoperable artefacts—such as data-quality descriptors, data-space-compatible metadata, cross-domain model documentation, risk-and-drift monitoring, and change-of-ownership controls. These toolchains support compliance in multi-stakeholder CPS and SoS environments where no single actor governs the full data pipeline, ensuring responsible AI evolution throughout data generation, exchange, analysis, and model deployment.

Scope: This recommendation focuses on creating open, modular, and interoperable toolchains that enable decentralised, data-sovereign AI across the full lifecycle of CPS and related domains such as systems-of-systems. Building on the need for cross-border data use without raw-data transfer, these toolchains support governance of sensitive, safety-critical, and legally constrained data in a manner consistent with European data-space principles and evolving regulatory requirements. They provide operational capabilities for managing data quality, training and validation, deployment, monitoring, accountability, and ownership change, while generating standardised and accessible assurance artefacts for regulators, operators, and other stakeholders. By emphasising trustworthy, compliance-ready, and practically usable mechanisms, rather than experimental performance, the scope aims to lower adoption barriers across Europe's industrial ecosystems and reinforce alignment with EU values on safety, transparency, sustainability, and fundamental rights. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Technology Recommendation F – *Open-up safety-security-performance interactions for real-world resilience and technology uptake in systems as markets.*

Rationale: *The need for automated, trustworthy management of safety, security, and performance (SSP) in complex systems is well-recognised^{[3][4]}. However, the traditional methods are still widely spread separating in particular the safety and security. This creates inefficiencies and barriers to industrial adoption of technologies that enable their joint treatment and governance. This, in turn, limits advances in automation and technology uptake. SSP represent separate disciplines, however in parallel there is an increasing pressure for advanced integrative research and management approaches to promote adaptability and resilience in both design and operational phases. Dedicated expertise should be encouraged to find solutions that maximise SSP interactions relevant for resilience. This is in contrast with general systems engineering that, due to a very wide scope, seeks to minimise SSP interactions, as for system architects, they are considered among the hardest decisions to make^[4]. A balanced solution needs to be found to avoid overly restricting uptake of all the contributing technologies to CPS and for system adaptability.*

These innovations should be used to evolve regulations towards adopting credible safety and security combined techniques and mediation. Due to the significant hurdles as a topic traversing knowledge domains, support R&D technologies should be established based on interdisciplinary best practice. The capacity to evaluate and compare SSP jointly is expected to bring major enhancements to design, operations and technology transfer, crucial for Europe's ability to adopt digital technologies effectively and address the needs for trustworthy systems. This will be as a result of significantly enlarging the permitted interactions between SSP mechanisms and benefitting from the increasingly pervasive interconnectivity. It will support many other technology advances such as AI/ML integration and the need to enable IoT systems to automatically integrate and coordinate within larger Systems of Systems (SoS), ensuring resilient operation and enhanced system capabilities.

Expected Outcomes:

- **Advanced SSP Approaches & Mechanisms:** *As a high-level support technology, establish an approach for joint SSP research. Extend applied technologies for coupling and combined analysis of safety, security, and performance, especially focused on AI\ML and IoT within systems of systems contexts.*
- **Regulatory Alignment:** *Propose updates to regulatory frameworks, supporting a convergence of SSP solutions and evolving industry standards and security requirements.*
- **Interdisciplinary Teaching and Collaboration:** *Foster educational programs and training to engage industry stakeholders, regulators, and researchers, facilitating a shared understanding of SSP trade-offs and adoption.*

Scope: The work will focus on developing and demonstrating advanced SSP coupling mechanisms and approaches including co-engineering in key sectors like transport, nuclear, oil, gas, first response and other safety-critical systems or extreme environments where dependability is essential. It will draw together the relevant building bricks for managing safety, security, and performance (SSP) and converge strategy for resilience. This includes assessing methodologies for aligning SSP with certification standards like the EU Cybersecurity Act, ISO 21443 and ISA/IEC 62443. The work will include system modelling, conducting scenario-based evaluations to demonstrate the benefits of advanced SSP coupling and propose solutions to barriers in certification and policy processes. Additionally, it will foster interdisciplinary collaboration and life-long learning schemes among stakeholders, including researchers, industry partners, and regulatory bodies, to ensure alignment with the future industry needs and regulatory requirements. As cross-disciplinary technology development – R&D preparing the destination environments is a particular challenge outside of normal exploitation actions. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Technology Recommendation G - Advance proactive risk management and analysis solutions *for enhanced dependability of systems interactions and for AI/ML.*

Rationale: *The growing complexity of interconnected critical systems and AI/ML integration in CPS necessitates a paradigm shift in dependability engineering. Traditional approaches treating safety only as a non-functional property are no longer adequate. A new perspective is required that considers Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, Safety, and Security (RAMS2) as functional properties at the system-of-systems level. Functional properties are typically treated as modules within a system, such as sensing, with a similar call now being made for orchestrating\governing properties like safety across many connected systems. This shift is necessary for addressing unique challenges posed by AI/ML-enabled CPS, where system-level specification flaws can lead to major incidents/accidents. Across critical sectors like smart energy grids and autonomous transportation, the integration of AI/ML introduces new vulnerabilities that traditional risk assessment methods may overlook. Historical examples, such as the Mars Climate Orbiter mishap and accidents like the autonomous taxi of Cruise, a subsidiary of General Motors, underscore the need for more sophisticated, proactive risk management strategies in the age of AI/ML-enabled CPS.*

Expected Outcomes:

- Develop advanced, **model-based functional hazard analysis techniques** like STPA especially on **man-machine teaming functions** and AI/ML-dependant CPS.
- Create comprehensive **risk assessment frameworks** addressing ethical, safety, and security implications of AI/ML in critical systems.
- Establish **dynamic, adaptive risk management strategies** and European standards for AI/ML safety and reliability in CPS.

Scope: This research initiative will develop cutting-edge proactive risk management and analysis solutions for AI/ML-enabled CPS. It will advance model-based System-of-Systems engineering techniques for hazard analysis, creating methodologies to capture complex interdependencies. The program will foster sophisticated simulation environments, incorporating adversarial testing and chaos engineering, to test complex system interactions before real-world deployment. A major focus will be integrating advanced diagnostics, prognostics, and health management capabilities for proactive fault detection and predictive maintenance in AI/ML-enabled CPS. The initiative will establish frameworks for continuous risk monitoring and automated contingency management, ensuring CPS can respond dynamically to emerging threats. Throughout, special attention will be given to aligning these enhanced risk analysis methods with European values and regulations, promoting ethical and responsible AI/ML-enabled CPS development. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Technology Recommendation H – Extend **online feedback mechanisms** for testing and validation in dependable systems.

Rationale: *Online feedback mechanisms are essential for enabling the uptake of AI/ML in dependable systems while addressing certification challenges. The EU AI Act’s definition of “significant change” creates friction for AI systems that learn or adapt after deployment, as each update could trigger re-assessment unless continuous validation ensures that behaviour remains within certified bounds. Digital Twin technologies with supervisory control can provide such continuous validation, enabling prediction, early intervention, and increased autonomy while maintaining assurance. Because sensor and environmental uncertainties affect system perception and control, uncertainty-aware runtime verification is necessary to ensure safety and security dynamically, complementing pre-deployment evidence that may not reflect operational variability.*

Expected Outcomes:

- **Supervisory digital twin validation** that continuously checks AI-enabled CPS behaviour against certified safety specifications, supporting higher levels of autonomy through runtime monitoring rather than relying solely on pre-deployment certification.
- **Uncertainty-aware runtime assurance** that quantifies and compensates for sensor, environmental, and model-related uncertainties, enabling assured decision-making in

supervisory control and ensuring safe human-AI collaboration when uncertainty thresholds are exceeded.

- **Dynamic AI validation frameworks** that verify operational safety of machine-learned models—covering out-of-distribution detection, confidence calibration, operational design domain monitoring, and update-specific safety checks providing scalable assurance evidence aligned with EU AI Act post-market monitoring requirements.

Scope: This recommendation supports R&D and applied technologies that integrate digital twins with runtime assurance for AI-enabled CPS. The scope includes predictive twin capabilities that detect deviations from certified bounds, alongside toolchains for uncertainty quantification, real-time monitoring, runtime verification, data-flow tracking, and automated compliance checks. It further covers protocols for validating AI model updates against safety requirements, including criteria for when formal re-assessment is needed. By providing reference frameworks and implementations, the work aims to lower barriers to adopting continuous assurance while supporting post-market monitoring obligations under the EU AI Act. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Scalable Infrastructure Capacity

Three recommendations are proposed here considering architectural and deployment technologies.

Technology Recommendation I – *With higher critical system interconnectivity, new and advanced systemic technologies for **performance characterisation** and for **isolation of hazards and threats** are needed.*

Rationale: *Modern CPS are evolving toward unprecedented levels of autonomy and interconnectivity, demanding increasingly sophisticated responses to variable physical environments. This evolution necessitates systems capable of highly dynamic behaviour, adapting their responses based on complex contextual factors with respect of real-time constraints imposed by the environment. The integration of AI technologies, coupled with advanced solutions for energy management, connectivity, new computing NCP platforms and digital twins, has dramatically increased the complexity of performance management across distributed systems.*

Critical systems now face a fundamental challenge: balancing the need for enhanced computational capabilities with strict certification requirements. For instance, in avionics, safety requirements demand failure rates as low as 10^{-10} for catastrophic events. Similar ultra-high reliability requirements are emerging across sectors as autonomous systems interact more directly with human lives. This creates a paradox where systems must simultaneously become more dynamic and demonstrably deterministic.

These competing demands—enhanced adaptability alongside more integrated dependability characterisation—require breakthrough technologies. We need new approaches to characterise and verify real-time behaviour in multi-tasking environments, especially when

dealing with AI/ML components. Traditional methods of performance analysis and hazard isolation become inadequate when systems must dynamically reallocate resources while maintaining strict safety guarantees.

Expected Outcomes:

- *Advanced **real-time performance methods** to master demonstrably deterministic multi-tasking environments, enabling **precise monitoring and control of system behaviour across distributed architectures.***
- ***Robust isolation mechanisms** for containing hazards and threats in interconnected critical systems, including guarded AI architectures that implement safety envelopes and deterministic fallback to certified behaviour, particularly in edge computing scenarios where performance demands meet safety requirements.*
- ***Verifiable performance bounds for AI/ML-enabled components in critical systems,** supported by runtime assurance techniques for continuous verification against specified bounds and detection of anomalous outputs, ensuring predictable behaviour while maintaining operational efficiency.*

Scope: This research addresses two critical challenges in modern cyber-physical systems: performance management and risk isolation—both significantly complicated by AI/ML integration. Advanced methodologies will be developed for real-time performance analysis in interconnected distributed and multicore architectures, with particular attention to variable workload scenarios and AI/ML integration. The work extends existing defence mechanisms in edge computing to prevent fault propagation across interconnected critical applications. New verification and validation techniques will be proposed for multi-tasking environments where current timing analysis methods prove insufficient. These methods will support systems with mixed-criticality levels and dynamic resource allocation. The research will produce analytical frameworks for early detection of performance limitations and security vulnerabilities, with specific emphasis on systems incorporating AI/ML components. This integrated approach to performance characterisation and safety isolation aims to advance the development of dependable CPS. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Technology Recommendation J — Hybrid Edge–Cloud Big Data Analytics for CPS

Rationale: *Cyber-physical systems (CPS) underpin many of Europe’s critical and strategic sectors, including mobility, energy, manufacturing, and infrastructure management. These systems increasingly depend on the continuous analysis of large data streams to operate safely, efficiently, and sustainably. Many CPS decisions must be taken within milliseconds and close to the physical system itself. At the same time, operators and public authorities require broader, cross-regional analytics to support optimisation, oversight, and resilience at European scale.*

This creates a structural challenge: data must be processed both locally and globally, while respecting latency constraints, energy efficiency, cybersecurity, and data-protection requirements. A hybrid edge–cloud approach responds directly to this challenge by distributing analytics across an edge–cloud continuum. It enables fast, local data processing where real-time response is critical, while still supporting large-scale analytics, coordination, and governance in the cloud.

To be effective at European level, such approaches must be interoperable across vendors, sectors, and operators, and compatible with Europe’s goals on data sovereignty and trusted data sharing. Common information models and data-space governance mechanisms are therefore essential enablers for scalable CPS analytics across supply chains and critical infrastructure.

Expected Outcomes:

- ***Edge–cloud analytics pipelines for CPS**, providing reference architectures and validated demonstrations that show how real-time edge analytics can be combined with cloud-based coordination and oversight across organizations and Member States. Mechanisms for data-sovereign cross-organisational analytics also to be considered.*
- ***Resilient and fail-safe CPS operation**, through design patterns that ensure systems can fall back to certified and deterministic control logic if AI-enabled components degrade, fail, or behave unpredictably.*
- ***Improved interoperability and vendor neutrality**, supported by reusable semantic descriptions and integration toolkits that allow heterogeneous CPS components to exchange data consistently across sectors.*

Scope: Hybrid edge–cloud analytics solutions should be developed and validated for representative cyber-physical systems (CPS) use cases across sectors such as transport, energy, and process industries. These solutions are expected to demonstrate compliance with strict latency, reliability, and energy-efficiency requirements at the edge, while simultaneously enabling large-scale analytics, optimization, and system management capabilities in the cloud. They should rely on common, interoperable descriptions of assets and data streams in order to facilitate seamless cross-vendor and cross-sector integration, thereby increasing cohesion and enhancing portability.

In addition, the solutions should embed robust governance mechanisms that enforce data-usage policies and ensure traceability and accountability across organizational boundaries, supporting trustworthy data sharing and collaboration. Comprehensive monitoring and observability mechanisms should also be integrated to measure and assess performance, safety, robustness, and environmental impact under real operating conditions. Overall, the emphasis should be placed on scalable and reusable approaches that can be broadly adopted across Europe, strengthening digital sovereignty and industrial competitiveness while enabling the reliable deployment of AI-enabled CPS in alignment with European values and regulatory frameworks. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential.*

Technology Recommendation K - Fleet-scale Trustworthy IIoT for Safety-Critical CPS (Zero Trust, Lifecycle Governance, and Modular Certification)

Rationale: *Industrial IoT devices are increasingly integrated into safety-critical control loops, where system faults or malicious attacks lead to severe physical consequences. Consequently, traditional perimeter-based security is insufficient for large-scale fleets with strict timing and reliability requirements. A crypto-agile zero-trust architecture is required to verify interactions continuously within the network. Furthermore, static certification approaches prohibit necessary security updates due to high costs and effort. Therefore, we must define lifecycle governance frameworks that support modular certification. This allows operators to manage updates and maintain dependability without performing extensive re-certification for every change.*

Expected Outcomes

- ***Crypto-agile Zero-trust IIoT architectures*** that implement continuous authentication and least privilege policies capable of adapting to advanced threats while satisfying strict **latency** and availability **constraints** for **safety-critical** loops.
- ***Lifecycle governance*** frameworks managing updates, credential rotation, and decommissioning, with defined responsibilities across the **supply chain**.
- ***Accountable edge intelligence*** solutions offering end-to-end traceability of data and **models**, supported by auditable **runtime** monitoring and rollback **paths**.

Scope: This recommendation focuses on developing and demonstrating scalable, crypto-agile zero-trust architectures for Industrial IoT fleets operating within safety-critical control loops. The work will establish standardized lifecycle governance frameworks that enable secure, continuous network updates, credential rotation, and accountable edge intelligence. A key priority is defining modular certification pathways across the supply chain, allowing operators to deploy necessary safety and security updates without incurring the prohibitive costs of full system re-certification. *Applying interdisciplinary best practices will be essential in this context.*

Conclusion

Cyber-Physical System research is a cornerstone of future innovation, integrating diverse technologies across sectors such as transportation, healthcare, and manufacturing. The recommendations outlined in this white paper address critical challenges for CPS research, focusing on enabling tools, managing cross-cutting needs between knowledge domains, and aligning technologies with emerging standards.

By advancing both support and applied R&D, the proposed strategies aim to simplify the complexities of integration, enhance dependability, and promote scalable, trusted solutions for highly interconnected systems. The transition of AI from experimental to operational and regulated status makes these recommendations particularly urgent. Centralized platforms, AI assurance frameworks aligned to regulatory requirements, controlled AI lifecycle management, human-AI teaming validation methods, and advanced methodologies for

system dependability will play an essential role for Europe's commitment to technological sovereignty and responsible AI deployment.

The vision for CPS requires collaboration among researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers, to bridge disciplinary gaps and accelerate the adoption of transformative technologies. Through collective effort, CPS research can unlock unprecedented advances, ensuring European leadership in global technology markets while addressing societal needs for safe, dependable, and adaptable systems.

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